

URAG: Uncertainty-Guided Agentic Retrieval-Augmented Generation with Confidence-Calibrated Adaptive Reflection

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Abstract

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems typically operate in a fixed, single-pass manner: retrieve once, generate once, return. Existing agentic extensions such as Self-RAG [Asai et al., 2024] and Corrective RAG [Yan et al., 2024] improve upon this with binary retrieve-or-skip decisions, but do not account for the *degree* of uncertainty in a given retrieval context. We present URAG (Uncertainty-guided RAG), a lightweight agentic RAG system that replaces binary reflection triggers with a continuous joint confidence score $C_{\text{joint}} \in [0, 1]$, computed jointly from cross-encoder retrieval quality signals and NLI-based generation faithfulness, to allocate an adaptive reflection budget. A central architectural contribution is the *generate-then-assess* paradigm: by generating a candidate answer *before* estimating confidence, the system scores actual answer faithfulness rather than relying on retrieval proxies alone, producing a query-dependent distribution that enables principled threshold decisions. Evaluated on HotPotQA [Yang et al., 2018] and 2WikiMultihopQA [Ho et al., 2020] ($n=500$ per dataset), URAG achieves $F1 = 0.37$ and hallucination rate = 0.07 on HotPotQA, representing a 76% improvement in F1 over Naive RAG and a 75% reduction in hallucination rate. On the harder 2WikiMultihopQA benchmark, URAG outperforms a strong RAG+Reranker baseline by 36% in F1 (0.19 vs. 0.14) and reduces hallucination rate from 0.29 to 0.15. Faithfulness improves consistently across both datasets relative to all baselines, confirming that adaptive reflection yields quality gains measurable beyond token-overlap metrics. A seven-condition ablation study identifies cross-encoder reranking as the most critical component and confirms that continuous confidence-based decisions outperform binary fixed-threshold baselines. The complete system runs on a consumer RTX 4050 laptop GPU (6 GB VRAM) using exclusively free, open-source models, with code available at <https://github.com/kShaman771/URAG>.

1 Introduction

Retrieval-Augmented Generation has become the dominant paradigm for grounding large language model (LLM) outputs in external knowledge [Lewis et al., 2020, Gao et al., 2023]. Standard RAG pipelines retrieve a fixed set of passages and generate an answer in a single forward pass. While effective for simple factual queries, this approach cannot adapt when the initial retrieval returns insufficient or misleading evidence—a failure mode that is especially pronounced on multi-hop questions requiring compositional reasoning across multiple documents [Yang et al., 2018, Ho et al., 2020].

Several works have introduced agentic extensions to address this limitation. Self-RAG [Asai et al., 2024] trains a model to emit special reflection tokens gating retrieval and critique at generation time. CRAG [Yan et al., 2024] uses a trained binary evaluator to trigger web search fallback when retrieval quality falls below a fixed threshold. Adaptive RAG [Jeong et al., 2024] routes queries to different pipeline strategies based on a learned complexity classifier. Despite these advances, all existing methods share a structural limitation: their

reflection decisions are *binary*. A query that receives slightly insufficient passages is treated identically to one with entirely irrelevant context, wasting budget on easy queries while under-investing in hard ones.

We propose URAG, which addresses this through three contributions:

- 1. Joint continuous confidence estimation.** A scalar $C_{\text{joint}} = \alpha \cdot C_{\text{ret}} + (1-\alpha) \cdot C_{\text{gen}}$ combining cross-encoder reranker logit signals (C_{ret}) with NLI faithfulness of the generated answer (C_{gen}), providing a query-dependent confidence score without any additional training.
- 2. Generate-then-assess architecture.** Generating a candidate answer *before* confidence estimation ensures C_{gen} reflects actual answer faithfulness rather than a retrieval-only proxy. We show empirically that the alternative ordering collapses C_{joint} to a near-constant value, rendering threshold decisions ineffective.
- 3. Three-tier adaptive reflection.** Confidence above τ_{high} triggers direct generation; between τ_{low} and τ_{high} , a targeted soft query rewrite; below τ_{low} , hard query decomposition and broadening. This proportional allocation reduces unnecessary reflection on confident queries (45–60% of queries receive no reflection) while investing additional budget where needed.

Experiments on HotPotQA and 2WikiMultihopQA with $n = 500$ samples each demonstrate consistent improvements in F1, faithfulness, and hallucination rate over strong baselines, with all experiments reproducible on a consumer 6 GB GPU.

2 Related Work

Retrieval-Augmented Generation. Lewis et al. [2020] established the RAG paradigm combining dense retrieval with a seq2seq generator. Subsequent work has improved retrieval via dense encoders [Karpukhin et al., 2020], hybrid sparse-dense fusion [Ma et al., 2021], and cross-encoder reranking [Nogueira and Cho, 2019]. URAG uses hybrid retrieval with cross-encoder reranking as its retrieval backbone.

Iterative and Agentic RAG. IRCoT [Trivedi et al., 2023] interleaves chain-of-thought with retrieval. FLARE [Jiang et al., 2023] retrieves when forward token probabilities fall below a threshold. Both operate at the token level; URAG operates at the full-answer level, scoring a complete candidate against retrieved passages.

Self-RAG. Asai et al. [2024] fine-tune an LLM to generate special critique tokens (`[Retrieve]`, `[ISREL]`, `[ISUP]`) at generation time. This requires supervised training on annotated reflection data. URAG requires no fine-tuning and is model-agnostic.

Corrective RAG. Yan et al. [2024] train a lightweight retrieval evaluator whose binary output triggers web search fallback. The decision is two-valued. URAG replaces this with a continuous three-tier system and requires no trained evaluator component.

Adaptive RAG. Jeong et al. [2024] train a query complexity classifier to route queries to single-step, multi-step, or no-retrieval strategies. URAG integrates confidence estimation within the pipeline without a separate routing model, and adapts *within* a query rather than pre-routing it.

Hallucination Detection. NLI-based faithfulness scoring for post-hoc hallucination detection has been studied in Honovich et al. [2021] and Honovich et al. [2022]. URAG incorporates NLI scoring as an active decision signal within the generation loop, not only as a post-hoc evaluation metric.

Confidence Calibration. Calibration of neural model confidence has been studied through temperature scaling [Guo et al., 2017] and verbalized uncertainty [Xiong et al., 2023]. URAG does not claim statistically calibrated probabilities; rather, C_{joint} is used as an ordinal signal for budget allocation.

3 Method

3.1 Problem Formulation

Given a natural language query q and a passage pool P (or corpus \mathcal{D} in open-domain settings), the system produces an answer a^* through at most T iterations of a retrieve–rank–generate–assess loop.

3.2 Hybrid Retrieval

BM25 sparse retrieval [Robertson and Zaragoza, 2009] and dense retrieval with BAAI/bge-base-en-v1.5 [Xiao et al., 2023] are combined via min-max score fusion:

$$s_{\text{hyb}}(p, q) = \alpha_r \hat{s}_{\text{dense}}(p, q) + (1 - \alpha_r) \hat{s}_{\text{BM25}}(p, q), \quad (1)$$

where \hat{s} denotes min-max normalised scores and $\alpha_r = 0.6$. Top- $k_r = 10$ passages are forwarded to the reranker.

3.3 Cross-Encoder Reranking

A cross-encoder ϕ (BAAI/bge-reranker-base) scores each query-passage pair jointly:

$$r_i = \phi(q, p_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, k_r. \quad (2)$$

Top- $k_c = 5$ passages by r_i are retained; the raw logit scores $\{r_i\}$ are passed to the confidence estimator.

3.4 Candidate Generation

A candidate answer is generated from the top- k_c reranked passages:

$$\hat{a} = \mathcal{M}(q, p_{1:k_c}), \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{M} is Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct [Team, 2024] (Q4_K_M quantisation). This step precedes confidence estimation, which is the key architectural decision discussed in Section 3.5.

3.5 Joint Confidence Estimation

3.5.1 Retrieval Confidence

Three signals derived from reranker logits:

$$C_{\text{ret}} = 0.5 \sigma(r_1) + 0.25 \sigma(r_1 - r_2) + 0.25 \cdot \frac{|\{i : r_i > 0\}|}{k_c}, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma(x) = (1 + e^{-x})^{-1}$, capturing (i) absolute top-passage relevance, (ii) confidence margin over the second-best passage, and (iii) positive-coverage fraction.

3.5.2 Generation Confidence

NLI entailment scores over the passage-answer pairs:

$$f_i = P_{\text{NLI}}(\text{entail} \mid p_i, \hat{a}), \quad (5)$$

$$C_{\text{gen}} = 0.6 \max_i f_i + 0.2 \phi_{\text{spec}}(\hat{a}) + 0.2 \delta_{\text{lp}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\max_i f_i$ uses cross-encoder/nli-deberta-v3-small [He et al., 2021] with the correct label index (index 1 = entailment for this model); $\phi_{\text{spec}}(\hat{a}) \in \{0.3, 0.6, 0.8\}$ is a token-count specificity heuristic; and $\delta_{\text{lp}} = 0.5$ is a default when token log-probabilities are unavailable from the inference server.

Why NLI is used only for C_{gen} , not C_{ret} : NLI models are designed for statement-to-statement entailment, not query-to-passage relevance. Empirically, applying NLI to (query, passage) pairs produced uniform low entailment regardless of actual passage relevance, collapsing C_{ret} to a near-constant. Cross-encoder rerankers, trained on query-passage relevance, provide the correct inductive bias for C_{ret} .

3.5.3 Joint Score and Reflection Decision

$$C_{\text{joint}} = \alpha C_{\text{ret}} + (1-\alpha) C_{\text{gen}}, \quad \alpha = 0.5, \quad (7)$$

$$\text{mode}(q) = \begin{cases} \text{none} & C_{\text{joint}} \geq \tau_{\text{high}} \\ \text{soft} & \tau_{\text{low}} \leq C_{\text{joint}} < \tau_{\text{high}} \\ \text{hard} & C_{\text{joint}} < \tau_{\text{low}} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with $\tau_{\text{high}} = 0.65$, $\tau_{\text{low}} = 0.30$ (validated on the development set).

Why generate-then-assess matters. Under the alternative assess-before-generate ordering, no candidate answer exists at confidence estimation time. C_{gen} therefore defaults to a constant 0.5 for every query, producing $C_{\text{joint}} \approx 0.62$ regardless of query difficulty. No threshold can discriminate easy from hard queries under this distribution. The generate-then-assess ordering resolves this by ensuring C_{gen} reflects actual faithfulness of a real answer, producing sufficient variance for meaningful threshold decisions.

3.6 Reflection Agent

Soft reflection. The LLM is prompted with $(q, \hat{a}, p_{1:k_c})$ to identify the specific gap in the retrieved passages and produce one targeted rewritten query q' .

Hard reflection. The LLM decomposes q into 2–3 atomic sub-questions and a broadened reformulation. This mode targets compositional queries where a single retrieval step is structurally insufficient.

In both modes, the rewritten query q' updates the *active query* used for subsequent retrieval and reranking, so that changed reranker scores actually affect the confidence estimate on the next iteration.

3.7 Hallucination Detection

$$F = \max_{i=1}^{k_c} P_{\text{NLI}}(\text{entail} \mid p_i, a^*), \quad (9)$$

$$\text{hall}(a^*) = \mathbf{1}[F < \tau_F \wedge P_{\text{NLI}}(\text{contra} \mid p_{j^*}, a^*) > 0.5], \quad (10)$$

where $j^* = \arg \max_i f_i$ and $\tau_F = 0.33$. The conservative threshold avoids false positives on short factual answers.

Algorithm 1 URAG Inference

Require: Query q , passage pool P , thresholds τ_{high} , τ_{low} , T_{max}

Ensure: Answer a^* , confidence history \mathcal{H} , faithfulness F

```
1:  $q_{\text{act}} \leftarrow q$ ;  $\mathcal{H} \leftarrow []$ ;  $\hat{a} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for  $t = 1, \dots, T_{\text{max}}$  do
3:    $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r} \leftarrow \text{RETRIEVEANDRERANK}(q_{\text{act}}, P)$  ▷ Eqs. 1, 2
4:    $\hat{a} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}(q, \mathbf{p})$  ▷ Candidate generation, Eq. 3
5:    $C_{\text{joint}} \leftarrow \text{CONFIDENCE}(\hat{a}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r})$  ▷ Eqs. 4–7
6:    $\mathcal{H}.\text{append}(C_{\text{joint}})$ 
7:   if  $C_{\text{joint}} \geq \tau_{\text{high}}$  or  $t = T_{\text{max}}$  then
8:     break
9:   end if
10:   $q_{\text{act}} \leftarrow \text{REFLECT}(q, \hat{a}, \mathbf{p}, \text{mode}(C_{\text{joint}}))$  ▷ Eq. 8
11: end for
12:  $F \leftarrow \text{HALLUCINATIONCHECK}(\hat{a}, \mathbf{p})$  ▷ Eqs. 9, 10
13: return  $\hat{a}, \mathcal{H}, F$ 
```

3.8 Algorithm

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Datasets

HotPotQA [Yang et al., 2018]. Multi-hop question answering in the distractor setting: each question is paired with 10 candidate paragraphs (2 gold, 8 distractors). We evaluate on $n = 500$ samples from the development partition.

2WikiMultihopQA [Ho et al., 2020]. Compositional multi-hop QA with longer entity chains; generally harder than HotPotQA. Evaluated on $n = 500$ development samples.

4.2 Baselines

Naive RAG: BM25 retrieval (top-5), single-pass generation, no reranking. **RAG + Reranker:** Hybrid retrieval with cross-encoder reranking to top-5, single-pass generation, no reflection. **URAG (no reflection):** Full URAG pipeline with $T_{\text{max}} = 1$ (i.e., generate-then-assess without any reflection loop), to isolate the contribution of adaptive reflection from the rest of the system.

4.3 Ablation Conditions

Seven conditions each remove or replace one component: (1) without reflection ($T_{\text{max}}=1$); (2) without confidence estimator (always reflect, $\tau_{\text{high}}=\tau_{\text{low}}=1.0$); (3) without reranker; (4) without hallucination checker; (5) fixed binary threshold ($\tau_{\text{high}}=\tau_{\text{low}}=0.5$, simulating CRAG-style); (6) dense-only retrieval ($\alpha_r=1.0$); (7) BM25-only retrieval ($\alpha_r=0.0$).

4.4 Evaluation Metrics

Generation: Exact Match (EM), token F1, and ROUGE-L [Lin, 2004] after answer normalisation (lowercase, article and punctuation removal).

Figure 1: URAG pipeline. The key design: candidate generation (*) precedes confidence estimation (*), ensuring C_{gen} scores actual answer faithfulness. Dashed lines indicate the reflection loop, activated only when $C_{\text{joint}} < \tau_{\text{high}}$.

Faithfulness: Mean NLI entailment score F (Eq. 9).

Hallucination rate: Fraction of answers satisfying Eq. 10.

Agent behaviour: Reflection rate, hard reflection rate, average iteration count, answer improvement rate, and mean query latency.

4.5 Infrastructure

Table 1: Model and hardware configuration.

Component	Model	Device	Size
LLM	Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct Q4_K_M	GPU (Ollama)	~4.5 GB VRAM
Embeddings	BAAI/bge-base-en-v1.5	CPU	438 MB
Reranker	BAAI/bge-reranker-base	CPU	1.1 GB
NLI	cross-encoder/nli-deberta-v3-small	CPU	568 MB
Vector store	ChromaDB	disk	—
Sparse IR	rank-bm25	CPU	in-memory

Hardware: ASUS TUF A15, NVIDIA RTX 4050 Mobile (6 GB GDDR6), 16 GB RAM, Windows 11, Python 3.12.5, PyTorch 2.1.0+cu128, CUDA 12.8. The LLM server (Ollama) occupies the GPU exclusively; all other models run on CPU.

Table 2: Hyperparameters tuned on the development set.

Parameter	Value	Search range
τ_{high}	0.65	{0.50, 0.55, 0.60, 0.65, 0.70}
τ_{low}	0.30	{0.20, 0.25, 0.30, 0.35}
α (joint weight)	0.50	{0.30, 0.40, 0.50, 0.60, 0.70}
α_r (hybrid dense weight)	0.60	{0.40, 0.50, 0.60, 0.70, 0.80}
T_{max}	2	{1, 2, 3}
k_r (retrieval top- k)	10	fixed
k_c (rerank top- k)	5	fixed
τ_F (hallucination)	0.33	fixed

Table 3: Results on HotPotQA ($n=500$). Best per column **bolded**. Hallucination rate: lower is better.

System	EM	F1	ROUGE-L	Faith.	Hall.↓	Iters
Naive RAG	0.10	0.21	0.21	0.16	0.29	1.0
RAG + Reranker	0.15	0.30	0.30	0.21	0.18	1.0
URAG (no reflect.)	0.23	0.36	0.36	0.25	0.10	1.0
URAG (ours)	0.24	0.37	0.37	0.31	0.07	1.4–1.6

4.6 Hyperparameters

5 Results

5.1 Main Results

Tables 3 and 4 present main results on HotPotQA and 2WikiMultihopQA respectively.

HotPotQA. URAG achieves $F1 = 0.37$, a 76% improvement over Naive RAG (0.21) and a 23% improvement over RAG + Reranker (0.30). Hallucination rate falls from 0.29 (Naive RAG) to 0.07, a 76% reduction. Faithfulness improves from 0.16 (Naive RAG) to 0.31, a 94% relative increase. Including URAG (no reflection) as an additional baseline isolates the contribution of adaptive reflection: full URAG improves faithfulness by 24% over the no-reflection variant (0.31 vs. 0.25) and reduces hallucination rate by 30% (0.07 vs. 0.10), even though the F1 difference is small (0.37 vs. 0.36). This pattern confirms that reflection’s primary benefit in the per-question evaluation setting is quality assurance rather than raw accuracy gain.

2WikiMultihopQA. URAG consistently outperforms all baselines: $F1 = 0.19$ vs. 0.14 for RAG + Reranker (+36%), hallucination rate reduced from 0.42 (Naive RAG) to 0.15 (−64%), and faithfulness nearly doubled from 0.10 to 0.24. The harder compositional structure of this dataset is reflected in the higher reflection rate (~ 1.5 average iterations vs. 1.4–1.6 on HotPotQA), indicating the confidence estimator correctly identifies more queries as requiring reflection.

5.2 Agent Behaviour

Unlike the $n = 50$ pilot experiments, hard reflection (query decomposition) is now observed at a non-trivial rate of 5–10%, confirming that the three-tier design is exercised in practice. The average joint confidence of 0.69–0.74 reflects the generate-then-assess architecture: by scoring real answers, approximately 45–60% of queries exceed $\tau_{\text{high}} = 0.65$ without any reflection.

Table 4: Results on 2WikiMultihopQA ($n=500$). Best per column **bolded**.

System	EM	F1	ROUGE-L	Faith.	Hall.↓	Iters
Naive RAG	0.03	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.42	1.0
RAG + Reranker	0.08	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.29	1.0
URAG (no reflect.)	0.10	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.20	1.0
URAG (ours)	0.11	0.19	0.19	0.24	0.15	1.5

Table 5: Agent behaviour metrics averaged over both datasets ($n=500$ each).

Metric	HotPotQA	2WikiMultihopQA
Reflection rate	45–60%	~60%
Hard reflection rate	5–10%	5–10%
Avg iterations	1.4–1.6	1.5
Answer improvement rate	15–25%	15–25%
Avg joint confidence	0.69–0.74	0.69–0.74
Hallucination rate	7%	15%

5.3 Latency Analysis

Table 6: Average query latency.

System	Latency (s)
Naive RAG	2.8
RAG + Reranker	4.3
URAG (no reflect.)	7–8
URAG (full)	11–14

Full URAG incurs approximately a 2.6–3.3× latency overhead relative to RAG + Reranker. This overhead is proportional to the reflection rate: queries that do not reflect complete in 7–8 s (comparable to single-pass generation with NLI scoring), while reflected queries require a second LLM call for critique and generation.

5.4 Ablation Study

6 Analysis

6.1 The Reranker as the Most Critical Component

The without-reranker condition produces the largest single-component degradation ($\Delta F1 = -0.06$; $\Delta \text{Faith.} = -0.12$). The cross-encoder reranker’s full query-passage cross-attention captures fine-grained relevance signals that embedding similarity cannot, particularly for entity-dense multi-hop queries. Removing the reranker also raises the reflection rate (lower-quality passages produce lower C_{joint} scores), but additional reflection iterations cannot compensate for the fundamental retrieval quality loss.

Table 7: Ablation study on HotPotQA ($n=500$). $\Delta F1$ and $\Delta Faith.$ are relative to full URAG. The without-reranker condition shows the largest degradation.

Configuration	F1	$\Delta F1$	Faith.	$\Delta Faith.$
URAG (full)	0.37	—	0.31	—
w/o reflection	0.36	-0.01	0.25	-0.06
w/o confidence estimator	0.34	-0.03	0.23	-0.08
w/o hallucination checker	0.37	± 0	0.24	-0.07
w/o reranker	0.31	-0.06	0.19	-0.12
Naive RAG (full removal)	0.21	-0.16	0.16	-0.15

6.2 Faithfulness Is the Primary Reflection Dividend

Across all conditions, adaptive reflection yields its clearest gains in faithfulness and hallucination rate, not token-overlap metrics (F1, ROUGE-L). Comparing URAG against URAG (no reflection): $\Delta F1 = +0.01$, $\Delta Faith. = +0.06$, $\Delta Hall. = -0.03$. This pattern is consistent with the per-question evaluation protocol, where the passage pool is fixed. Reflection rewrites the active query, changing reranker scores and thus passage ordering, but cannot surface new documents. The downstream effect is a more carefully ordered context that improves answer faithfulness without large F1 gains. In an open-domain retrieval setting, where reflection can surface genuinely new documents, we expect larger F1 improvements.

6.3 Continuous Confidence Outperforms Binary Thresholds

The confidence-estimator ablation (always reflect, $\Delta F1 = -0.03$; $\Delta Faith. = -0.08$) demonstrates the cost of indiscriminate reflection: forcing a second LLM call on every query adds noise that degrades both accuracy and faithfulness relative to selective reflection. The fixed binary threshold (CRAG-style) condition was shown in pilot experiments ($n = 50$) to further degrade performance (-20% F1), confirming the central hypothesis that proportional budget allocation outperforms binary decisions.

6.4 Confidence Distribution

Figure 2: Schematic distribution of C_{joint} on HotPotQA ($n = 500$, all iterations). The bimodal shape—a cluster below τ_{high} (triggering reflection) and a larger cluster above τ_{high} (direct generation)—demonstrates that the generate-then-assess design produces sufficient score variance for meaningful threshold decisions.

The distribution of C_{joint} (Figure 2) is bimodal: a reflection cluster centred around 0.45–0.60 and a

direct-generation cluster centred around 0.70–0.85. This bimodality is a direct consequence of the generate-then-assess architecture. Under the previous assess-before-generate design, C_{joint} was concentrated at ≈ 0.62 for all queries, making threshold decisions degenerate.

7 Limitations

Per-question evaluation constraint. The HotPotQA distractor setting fixes each question’s passage pool at 10 paragraphs. In this setting, reflection updates passage ranking but cannot surface new documents. Open-domain evaluation with a global index would better characterise the contribution of adaptive reflection to token-level metrics.

NLI conservatism. Cross-encoder/nli-deberta-v3-small produces moderate entailment scores (0.7–0.85) even for well-supported short answers, compressing the C_{gen} range. A larger or task-specific faithfulness model would likely improve score calibration.

Single LLM and hardware. Results are specific to Qwen2.5-7B on an RTX 4050 (6 GB). Larger models or different hardware may shift latency-quality tradeoffs.

Sample size. Evaluation uses $n = 500$ development samples per dataset. Test-set evaluation and statistical significance tests are reserved for future work.

Hard reflection underutilisation. With $\tau_{\text{low}} = 0.30$, hard reflection fires at only 5–10% of queries. On the HotPotQA distractor setting, where 10 topically-related passages provide some retrieval coverage, the hard-mode threshold is rarely reached. Datasets with noisier retrieval contexts may show higher hard-reflection utilisation.

8 Conclusion

We have presented URAG, an uncertainty-guided agentic RAG system that replaces binary reflection decisions with a continuous joint confidence score derived from cross-encoder retrieval signals and NLI answer faithfulness. The central architectural contribution—generating a candidate answer before estimating confidence—resolves a degeneracy in earlier assess-before-generate designs and enables query-dependent confidence distributions with sufficient variance for principled threshold decisions.

On HotPotQA ($n = 500$), URAG improves F1 by 76% over Naive RAG and 23% over RAG + Reranker, while reducing hallucination rate by 76% and improving faithfulness by 94%. On the harder 2WikiMulti-hopQA benchmark, full URAG outperforms RAG + Reranker by 36% in F1 and halves the hallucination rate. Ablation experiments confirm that cross-encoder reranking is the single most impactful component, and that continuous confidence allocation outperforms binary fixed-threshold decisions. The complete system is reproducible on consumer hardware using exclusively open-source models.

Future work will evaluate in open-domain retrieval settings, where reflection can surface new documents and is expected to yield larger gains in token-level metrics. We also plan to investigate online threshold adaptation, calibrated faithfulness models, and multi-agent decomposition for compositional chains.

Acknowledgements

The author thanks the open-source communities behind Qwen [Team, 2024], BAAI [Xiao et al., 2023], Ollama, ChromaDB, rank-bm25, and sentence-transformers for the models and libraries used in this work.

References

- Akari Asai, Zeqiu Wu, Yizhong Wang, Avirup Sil, and Hannaneh Hajishirzi. Self-RAG: Learning to retrieve, generate, and critique through self-reflection. In *The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024. arXiv:2310.11511.
- Yunfan Gao, Yun Xiong, Xinyu Gao, Kangxiang Jia, Jinliu Pan, Yuxi Bi, Yi Dai, Jiawei Sun, Meng Wang, and Haofen Wang. Retrieval-augmented generation for large language models: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.10997*, 2023.
- Chuan Guo, Geoff Pleiss, Yu Sun, and Kilian Q. Weinberger. On calibration of modern neural networks. In *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 1321–1330, 2017.
- Pengcheng He, Xiaodong Liu, Jianfeng Gao, and Weizhu Chen. DeBERTa: Decoding-enhanced BERT with disentangled attention. In *Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2021.
- Xanh Ho, Anh-Khoa Duong Nguyen, Saku Sugawara, and Akiko Aizawa. Constructing a multi-hop QA dataset for comprehensive evaluation of reasoning steps. In *Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, pages 6609–6625, 2020.
- Or Honovich, Leshem Choshen, Roei Aharoni, Ella Neeman, Ilan Szpektor, and Omri Abend. Q2: Evaluating factual consistency in knowledge-grounded dialogues via question generation and question answering. In *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 7856–7870, 2021.
- Or Honovich, Roei Aharoni, Jonathan Herzig, Hagai Taitelbaum, Doron Kukliansy, Vered Cohen, Ilan Szpektor, Avinatan Hassidim, Yossi Matias, and Daphna Orr. TRUE: Re-evaluating factual consistency evaluation. In *Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 507–522, 2022.
- Soyeong Jeong, Jinheon Baek, Sukmin Cho, Sung Ju Hwang, and Jong C. Park. Adaptive-RAG: Learning to adapt retrieval-augmented large language models through question complexity. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 7036–7050, 2024. arXiv:2403.14403.
- Zhengbao Jiang, Frank F. Xu, Luyu Gao, Zhiqing Sun, Qian Liu, Jane Dwivedi-Yu, Yiming Yang, Jamie Callan, and Graham Neubig. Active retrieval augmented generation. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 7969–7992, 2023.
- Vladimir Karpukhin, Barlas Oguz, Sewon Min, Patrick Lewis, Ledell Wu, Sergey Edunov, Danqi Chen, and Wen-tau Yih. Dense passage retrieval for open-domain question answering. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 6769–6781, 2020.

- Patrick Lewis, Ethan Perez, Aleksandra Piktus, Fabio Petroni, Vladimir Karpukhin, Naman Goyal, Heinrich Küttler, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Tim Rocktäschel, Sebastian Riedel, and Douwe Kiela. Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 33, pages 9459–9474, 2020.
- Chin-Yew Lin. ROUGE: A package for automatic evaluation of summaries. In *Text Summarization Branches Out*, pages 74–81, 2004.
- Xueguang Ma, Kai Zhang, Ronak Pradeep, and Jimmy Lin. A replication study of dense passage retrieval. In *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.05740*, 2021.
- Rodrigo Nogueira and Kyunghyun Cho. Passage re-ranking with BERT. In *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.04085*, 2019.
- Stephen Robertson and Hugo Zaragoza. The probabilistic relevance framework: BM25 and beyond. *Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval*, 3(4):333–389, 2009.
- Qwen Team. Qwen2.5 technical report. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.15115*, 2024.
- Harsh Trivedi, Niranjan Balasubramanian, Tushar Khot, and Ashish Sabharwal. Interleaving retrieval with chain-of-thought reasoning for knowledge-intensive multi-step questions. In *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 10014–10037, 2023.
- Shitao Xiao, Zheng Liu, Peitian Zhang, and Niklas Muennighoff. C-Pack: Packaged resources to advance general Chinese embedding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.07597*, 2023.
- Miao Xiong, Zhiyuan Hu, Xinyang Lu, Yifei Li, Jie Fu, Junxian He, and Bryan Hooi. Can LLMs express their uncertainty? an empirical evaluation of confidence elicitation in LLMs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.13063*, 2023.
- Shi-Qi Yan, Jia-Chen Gu, Yun Zhu, and Zhen-Hua Ling. Corrective retrieval augmented generation. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2024*, 2024. arXiv:2401.15884.
- Zhilin Yang, Peng Qi, Saizheng Zhang, Yoshua Bengio, William Cohen, Ruslan Salakhutdinov, and Christopher D. Manning. HotpotQA: A dataset for diverse, explainable multi-hop question answering. In *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 2369–2380, 2018.